

REFORMING INDIA'S EXAMINATION SYSTEM: A STUDY OF GLOBAL ALIGNMENTS IN NEP 2020

Anindita Banerjee

Assistant Professor, Lokenath B. Ed. College, Habra,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Evaluation plays a pivotal role in ensuring students' academic accountability, promoting students' success and preparing them for future challenges and opportunities. NEP 2020 is introduced to catalyze a paradigm shift in India's education system. The objectives of this study are to explore the evaluation and examination reforms proposed by NEP 2020 followed by Vedic philosophy, identify potential implementation hurdles and suggest strategies for effective execution. The research design of this study is qualitative, incorporating a range of sources, namely research articles, policy documents, governmental reports and empirical data. The findings of this study indicate that the holistic assessment (Purna), competency based progression (Swadhyay), focus on critical thinking (Tarka), emphasis on experimental learning (Anubhava) and continuous evaluation are the main features of the evaluation system as discussed in NEP 2020. The investigation revealed some challenges like infrastructural requirements, teachers' training, attitude and cultural problems and its possible actions to ensure the effective execution of the reforms. The adaptations and subsequent modifications in NEP 2020 evaluation system clearly aim to transform India's education system to create a more inclusive and student centred evaluation process.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Evaluation System, Vedic Philosophy, Holistic development, Examination reforms.

INTRODUCTION

The ancient Indian Education System, which dates back to the Vedic period, emphasized holistic development, spiritual growth and intellectual exploration of the students. The evaluation strategies utilised during this period were unique and focused on assessing students' knowledge, skills and character. National Education Policy 2020 is a comprehensive framework for education in India, formulated by Ministry of Human Resource Development. This policy marks a revolution in Indian Education, aiming to transform the country's education system by 2040. India's educational landscape was transformed with the introduction of the first National Education Policy in 1968 by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi, followed by the second Policy in 1986 under Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi's leadership. As the landscape of knowledge evolves, NEP 2020 emerges as a vital replacement for the 1986 policy, catalyzing transformative change. NEP 2020 introduces comprehensive evaluation and examination reforms in India aiming to transform the assessment landscape. NEP 2020 seeks to establish an Indian ethos-driven education system

that fosters equitable, holistic development, and making India a beacon of knowledge excellence worldwide. The present study will explore NEP 2020's evaluation and examination system reforms.

Among its myriad provisions, the policy's examination and evaluation reforms stand out as a bold attempt to revitalize the assessment framework, shifting the focus from rote learning to competency based evaluations. This paradigm shift aims to alleviate the long standing ills of India's examination system, including exam stress and inadequate emphasis on skills development.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Chandramana, & Kurien (2010) have advocated a study on NEP 2020, followed by its impact, challenges etc. It outlined notable features of NEP and analysed how the policies' recommendations inspire the present education system.

Aithal & Aithal (2020) emphasized different initiatives declared in the higher education system and compare them presently implemented system. They have discussed numerous transformations and estimated implementation strategies of NEP 2020 on the Indian Higher Education System.

Hemant Kumar & Joshi (2021) have analysed the importance of examination reforms suggested by NEP 2020. They have focused on changes required in the examination strategies and also highlighted multilingualism in school education. Finally the paper has suggested the necessities of proper planning and plotting new achievement cards in a new fashion.

Jayadeeshwaraiah (2023) has identified assessment and evaluation reforms of NEP 2020 and emphasized policy's aim in examinations' reforms. The study also analyzed the opportunities and challenges in implementation of NEP 2020 in present education system.

Bandgar (2024) in his research emphasizes that implementing assessment reforms in India's education system, as outlined in NEP 2020, poses significant challenges, including inadequate teacher training, technological limitations which must be addressed to align with global standards and achieve successful reform outcomes.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The present study on evaluation and examination reforms under the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 contributes significantly to the transformation of India's Education Landscape. By examining the policy's provisions for competency-based assessments, reduction in exam stress, and promotion of holistic development, this study provides valuable insights into the potential impact on students' learning outcomes and teachers' professional development. The rationale behind this research lies in addressing the long-standing issues plaguing India's examination system, including rote learning, high-stakes testing, and inadequate emphasis on skills development. By investigating the efficacy of NEP 2020's reforms, this study informs policymakers, educators and stakeholders on strategies to enhance the quality, equity and

accessibility of education in India. Ultimately, this aims to bridge the gap between policy intent and implementation reality, ensuring that NEP 2020's vision for a student-centric, flexible and innovative evaluation system becomes a tangible reality.

Figure 1 : Contribution of the Study

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the evaluation and examination reforms in the light of Vedic philosophy.
- To find out the potential implementation hurdles to be faced by the institutions.
- To find out strategies to overcome the challenges.

METHODOLOGY

The present study employs a qualitative research methodology to explore the examination and evaluation reforms outlined in the NEP 2020. The study incorporates journal articles, policy documents, Government reports etc. Overall the study follows comprehensive and holistic discussion on illustrating the essence of examination reforms suggested by NEP 2020.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) introduces significant reforms to India's assessment and examination system, aligning with global best practices. By shifting from rote-learning to competency-based assessment, the policy emphasizes critical thinking, creativity & problem-solving skills. This holistic approach to assessment, coupled with formative evaluations and flexibility in subject choices, aims to foster a more comprehensive understanding of student abilities. As India integrates its education system with global standards, the reforms will enhance the international recognition and comparability of Indian qualifications, ultimately preparing students for a more interconnected & competitive world.

OUTLINE OF NEP 2020, ITS EVALUATION AND EXAMINATION REFORMS

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is indeed a comprehensive and visionary plan that aims to transform India's education system from the Ground up. It is established on five core principles : Access, Equity, Quality Affordability and Accountability, with the ultimate goal of making India a global knowledge super power. NEP 2020 seeks to overhaul the existing education structure, introducing a new framework that's more flexible, inclusive and focused on developing both cognitive and social skills. This includes a major shift from the traditional 10 + 2 model to a more modular 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 design covering students from ages 3 to 18.

NEP 2020 priorities the overhaul of outdated assessment procedures, embracing innovative evaluation methodologies, enhancing competency based evaluations. It revolutionizes evaluation by shifting from traditional exam-centric assessments to a diverse, holistic framework. This transformation reflects India's dedication to equipping students with 21st century skills, aligning with international education benchmark.

VEDIC ELEMENTS IN NEP 2020 EVALUATION REFORMS

It is notable that Vaidik wisdom meets modern evaluation and examination reforms suggested by NEP 2020. NEP 2020's aim is the transform India's education landscape. Its evaluation and examination reforms prioritize competency-based learning, critical thinking and holistic development. Interestingly, these reforms resonate with the ancient Vedic philosophy, which emphasises, self-realisation, inquiry and balance.

Atma-Sakshatkar	⇒	Self-realisation
Vichara	⇒	Inquiry and Critical Thinking
Panch Kosha	⇒	Holistic Development
Advaya	⇒	Interconnectedness
Rita	⇒	Balance and Harmony

NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020: FEATURES OF ASSESSMENT

NEP 2020 priorities on transforming assessment for optimizing learning with a focus on the following :

Features of Assessment

- Regular, formative and competency based progression.
- Promoting learning and development of students.
- Testing of higher order skills (analysis, critical, thinking and conceptual clarity)
- Revising persistently the teaching learning processes to maximise academic achievements.

Aims of Assessment

- 1) Continuous, formative, competency based evaluation.
- 2) Foster learning and development of students.

- 3) Fostering a culture of assessment for learning.
- 4) Test high order skills (analytical and critical analysis)
- 5) Revising teaching learning process to optimise learning.

BRIEF DISCUSSION ON EVALUATION REFORMS SUGGESTED BY NEP 2020

1. Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation

NEP 2020 involves a continuous and progressive assessment of students' development throughout the academic year. This approach prioritizes frequent monitoring of students' progress.

Continuous assessment

Rather than relying on occasional assessments, this continuous and comprehensive evaluation component involves ongoing evaluation and tracking of students' development throughout the academic period. This component replaces intermittent testing with consistent, longitudinal monitoring of students' growth and achievement.

Comprehensive Evaluation

NEP 2020 emphasises comprehensive evaluation to assess students' learning outcomes. This comprehensive evaluation shifts from summative in formative assessments. It emphasises on continuous and comprehensive evaluation by focusing conceptual understanding and application and makes an integration of 21st century skills and values. Regular feedback and self-assessment are necessary in this concern.

Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation evaluates students comprehensively, integrating academic achievements with extracurricular engagement, interpersonal skills, conduct and emotional intelligence.

It assesses students' development beyond grades, considering extracurricular involvement, character, social abilities and mental health for a complete picture.

Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation seeks to empower students and teachers with prompt, constructive evaluations, highlighting strengths and weaknesses to inform supportive strategies.

This innovative model synthesises the strengths of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation and introduces a holistic evaluation paradigm. This NEP 2020s' evaluation reform promotes a broader range of educational experiences and shifting focus from summative assessments (Sengupta, 2020).

2. Vedic Concepts Supporting Continuous Assessment

In Vedic philosophy, knowledge is considered a continuous process, echoing the concept of continuous assessment. SWAHYAYA (Self-study) encourages continuous learning and self-assessment. SATSANGA (association with wise ones) fosters continuous feedback and growth. ATMA NIVEDANA (Self-surrender) promotes humility and openness to continuous learning. Vidya (knowledge) emphasises self-awareness (Atma-Vidya) and introspection (Antar-mukha) mirroring continuous assessments which focus on self-evaluation.

3. Holistic Report Card

The new report card, recommended by NEP 2020, adopts a multidimensional approach, recording students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor progress in nuanced detail. It enhanced on 360-degree evaluation of learners' growth.

Figure 2: Holistic Report Card

The assessment framework governed by NEP 2020 will integrate self-assessment, peer feedback and ongoing monitoring of students' performance in projects, group work, quizzes and inquiry based activities, alongside teacher evaluations.

4. Practical Evaluation

The National Education Policy 2020 emphasizes practical evaluation as a crucial aspect of assessing students learning outcomes, shifting focus from rote memorization to hands-on application. To achieve this NEP 2020 recommends integrating project based assessments, experiments, internships and vocational training into the curriculum. This approach encourages students to apply theoretical knowledge to real world problems, fostering critical thinking, creativity and problem solving skills. By incorporating practical evaluation, NEP 2020 aims to prepare students for the work force, entrepreneurship and lifelong learning, aligning with the policy's vision of developing knowledgeable, skilled and empathetic individual.

Here it must be mentioned that experimental learning embodies Vedic thoughts which focus on direct experience (ANUBHAVA).

5. Simplifying and Making Board Examination Easier

While the NEP 2020 offers valuable suggestions for board exams, the core emphasis should be on assessing essential skills rather than simplifying the assessment. Reducing exam pressure through subject choices and repeated attempts may alleviate exam stress, and meaningful education reform hinges on revitalising examination questions to assess deeper understanding. It is to be noted that when students consistently score 10% in literature, it signals failure in assessment methodology, particularly in question formulation and model answer creation.

Here are showing Revitalising Assessment Structure for grades 9 – 12, incorporating

board exams.

- Simplified assessment framework prioritises core capacities.
- Multitiered evaluation framework : annual / semester / modular assessments.
- Standard and regulations will be drafted by NCERT, in collaboration with SCERT, BoEs and PARAKH.
- Educators must be equipped for assessment reform by 2022–23 academic session.
- Each Board maintains parity in academic achievement standards.
- PARAKH National Center sets educational quality benchmarks like standards, norms and guidelines. It encourages institutions to adopt new assessment patterns of the 21st century.

6. 360 Degree Multidimensional Report Card for all Students :

The 360-degree multidimensional report card recommended by the National Education Policy (NEP, 2020) is a comprehensive assessment tool that evaluates students’ holistic development.

Figure 3: 360 Degree Multidimensional Evaluation

Table 1: Components of 360 Degree Evaluation

Area	Components
1. Academic Performance	→ Subject-wise grades. → Skill based assessments, i.e. critical thinking, problem-solving.
2. Co-Scholastic	→ Life Skills (communication, team work). → Values and attitudes (empathy, integrity). → Physical Education and sports. → Arts and cultural activities.

Area	Components
3. Personal and Social Development	→ Self-awareness and Self-management → Social awareness and relationships, emotional intelligence.
4. Extracurricular Activities	→ Participation in clubs, societies and community service. → Leadership and initiative.
5. Self-assessment and reflection	→ Students' self-evaluation of strengths, weakness and goals.

7. Digital or Technology Enhanced Assessment Tools

The National Education Policy 2020 emphasises the importance of technology-enabled assessment tools to enhance the evaluation process in education technology based assessments will improve the objectivity and efficiency of evaluation activities. The online and offline assessments, both may cater to diverse students' needs. Apart from these –

- AI-powered assessment tools for adaptive testing.
- Automated evaluation systems to reduce manual errors.
- Data analytics for insights on students' performance. Blending of technology in assessment recommended by NEP 2020.

Fig. 4 : Practical Evaluation

IMPLEMENTATION OF NECESSARY STRATEGIES FOR COMBATING HURDLES

NEP introduces transformative examination reforms, shifting focus from summative to formative assessments, but faces significant implementation hurdles. The reforms aims to promote

competency-based progression, holistic progress cards and redesigned assessment frameworks, emphasising conceptual understanding over rote learning. However, infrastructural gaps, inadequate teachers' training and funding constraints pose significant challenges. Additionally, resistance to change, capacity building and technology integration issues must be addressed.

1. Teachers' Training

Implementing examination reforms poses some challenges. Teachers' training hurdle is one of them. It includes capacity building of educators, enhancing content knowledge, leveraging Edtech for effective assessment, sufficient pedagogical training mindset shift etc.

To address these hurdles, the policy recommends continuous professional development programs, workshops and training sessions. Effective implementation requires collaborative efforts between governments, educational institutions and teachers. This policy also proposes a bold overhaul of Indian teacher education with a 4 year integrated B. Ed. becoming mandatory by 2030.

2. Infrastructural Gaps

The National Education Policy 2020 introduces transformative examination reforms, shifting focus from summative to formative assessments, to promote competency based progression, holistic progress cards, and redesigned assessment frameworks. However the effective implementation of evaluation reforms faces significant infrastructural gaps including inadequate classrooms, laboratories, technology infrastructure, libraries and sports facilities.

These limitations hinder the conduct of project based evaluations, technology-enhanced assessments and experiential learning, essential for developing critical thinking problem solving and creativity skills.

To bridge these gaps, NEP 2020 recommends investing in school infrastructure development, leveraging public-private partnerships and implementing digital initiatives. Prioritising inclusive and accessible infrastructure is crucial to ensure equitable access to quality education.

Table 2 : Hurdles and Strategies

Hurdles	Strategies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inadequate classrooms and labs. ● Insufficient resources and libraries. ● Invest in infrastructure development. ● Implement digital initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited technology infrastructural. ● Poor sanitation and hygiene facilities. ● Leverage public-private partnerships. ● Prioritize inclusive and accessible infrastructure.

3. Harmonizing with Established Assessment Framework

The alignment with established examination board and system is another remarkable challenge in the implementation of assessment reforms. This alignment may minimize disruption, enhance credibility and improve comparability across boards and institutions.

To ensure seamless integration, NEP 2020 aligns with existing examination boards, such as CBSE, ICSE and state boards, by mapping objectives to existing curricula, integrating competency-based progression with assessment frameworks, and harmonizing competency-based progression with assessment frameworks and also harmonizing holistic progress cards with report card systems.

Effective alignment will facilitate a smooth transition for students and teachers, leveraging existing resources and infrastructure while promoting innovative assessments.

4. Cultural and Societal Mindset of Assessment

NEP 2020 introduces transformative assessment reforms face implementation hurdles. Cultural and Societal mindset and perception is one of the significant obstacle which includes resistance to change from traditional rote learning, emphasis on grades over learning outcomes, and societal pressure for high stakes examination, and teachers' mindset pose significant hurdles.

Addressing these hurdles requires awareness campaigns, stakeholders engagement, teachers' training, community outreach, emphasising skills development and life-long learning.

Effective implementation demands a cultural shift prioritising competency-based progression and inclusive assessments that value diversity and promote equity. Apart from policy makers and educational institutions should involve parents and community members in educational decision-making.

NEP 2020'S EXAMINATION REFORMS AND THEIR ALIGNMENT WITH GLOBAL APPROACHES

The National Education Policy 2020 introduces transformative examination reforms, aligning with global best practices. Shifting from Summative to formative assessments, NEP 2020 emphasises competency-based progression, reduces high-stakes exams and integrates technology-enhanced assessments. These reforms mirror global approaches, such as Finland's competency-based assessments, Singapore's technology-enhanced assessments and Australia's authentic and performance tasks. By adopting these international standards, India aims to improve learning outcomes, enhance employability increase global competitiveness. This policy focus on self-assessment, peer review and inclusive evaluation methods also resonates with UNESCO's and OECD's recommendations. Effective implementation of these reforms will require stakeholder engagement, resource allocation and addressing equity and accessibility concerns.

CONCLUSION

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 marks a transformative shift in India's education landscape, introducing competency based progression, holistic progress cards and redesigned assessment frameworks. These evaluation and assessment reforms aim to cultivate critical thinking creativity and skills development aligning with global best practices. Effective

implementation requires addressing cultural and societal perception hurdles, investing in teachers' training and leveraging technology. NEP 2020's global focuses include inclusivity, equity and sustainability, mirroring UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4). As India strides towards a knowledge-based economy, NEP 2020's reforms will foster a future-ready workforce, enhance international collaborations and solidify India's position as a global leader in Education. At last it may be said that NEP 2020's emphasis on global perspectives cultivates the idea of global family.

‘AyamBandhurayamNetiGananaLaghuchetasam
UdaraCharitanam to VasudhaivaKutumbakam

(Mundak Upanishad)

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